

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CONCRETE SAMPLING USING WASTE GLASS AS FILLER

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Abstract

In recent years, industrial development has increased the amount of waste. Only 10% of waste is recycled. The rest of them become sources of environmental pollution as waste. On the other hand, such waste remains unused despite the presence of valuable components in it. This pollutes the environment by scattering its parts around, and causes soil erosion as a result of not filling the excavated soil cavities. In addition, deep dug ditches affect the change in the level and direction of underground water. This, in turn, has a negative impact on ecological stability. A large amount of solid waste is generated from mining until the product is produced. Other sources of such waste are large factories with high production capacity. Today, due to the rapid growth of the human population, as well as the proliferation of large industrial facilities with high production capacity, the amount of waste generated is constantly growing.

Keywords: cement, waste glass, filler, strength, concrete.

Introduction. One of the main places among wastes polluting the environment is occupied by solid wastes from industrial areas. These wastes are scattered around and pollute the useful land areas. This, in turn, creates environmental problems that are waiting to be solved. As industry develops, such sources of waste also expand. Every year, a large amount of solid waste is released into the environment during the exploitation and processing of geological exploration and mineral resources. Industrial enterprises that generate the most solid waste are household waste, metallurgy and machine building, thermal plants, used tires of end-of-life vehicles, electrical and electronic equipment, etc. They have a big ecological impact on the environment. Depletion of existing resources makes it urgent to use such wastes as a potential source of raw materials. In order

to use less natural resources, reduce environmental pollution and energy costs, the use of industrial waste is becoming a more and more important issue [1,2].

Raw materials and used materials.

Cement. The cement industry produces special cements designed for concrete use conditions and purposes. Sufficient diversity of cement types is achieved by adding different substances based on portland cement clinker. Portland cement with hydraulic additives (pussolan portland cement) - hardens more slowly than Portland cement. Concrete in such cement is more waterproof and durable, but it breaks down more easily under the influence of frost. As a result of the inclusion of calcium hydroaluminate sulfate in the composition of Portland cement, conditions for the formation of hydrosulfoaluminate are created.

Table 1

Mineralogical composition of cement

№	Minerals			
	Names	Formula	Conventional sign	Approximate content of clinker, %
1.	2 calcium silicate (belite)	$2\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2$	C_2S	17– 35
2.	3 calcium silicate (allite)	$3\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2$	C_3S	34 – 56
3.	3 calcium aluminate	$3\text{CaO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$	C_3A	6– 15
4.	3 calcium alumoferrite	$3\text{CaO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$	C_4A	11 – 23

The chemical composition of cement is as follows.

Table 2

Chemical composition of cement

Oxides	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃
Amount, %	66-67	23-28	5-12	12-15

Sand and glass. The amount of waste bottles produced in production is 0.25 million tons per year. In addition, glass occupies 5-7% of the total volume of household waste, which is approximately 1.3-1.9 million tons annually [3].

Glass waste with a fraction size of 0-20 mm and mass density of 1402 kg/m³ was used in the research. Natural sand was used as pomegranate filler for concrete preparation.

Granite gravel with 5-10 and 10-20 mm fraction, natural sand as fine aggregate and crushed sand were used to study the possibilities of glass used as a filler for concrete production. Glass sand with a fractional size of 0-20 mm from granite rock was included in the plastic concrete mixture in the amount of 0, 30, 50, 70 and 100% of the mass of fine aggregate.

In the studies, the optimal compositions of concrete for specific tasks were selected. Mobility of concrete mixtures was taken in the range of 4 to 8 cm [4].

The chemical composition of the glass is given in table 3.

Table 3

Chemical composition of waste glass used as filler.

Chemical element	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O+K ₂ O	SO ₃
Percent %	71,6-73,8	0,23-3,34	1,6-3,3	5,3-9,2	0,1-0,5	15,3-16,1	up to 0,2

Crushed sand meets the requirements of GOST 8736-2014 with a particle size of 0.63 mm.

3.05% of the waste glass consists of grains with a size of 10-20 mm, and 29.66% of grains with a size of 5-10 mm. The amount of dust and clay particles in natural sand is 0.7% by weight (standards GOST 8736-2014 - up to 6%), in gravel sand from granite rocks - 0.1%. There is no clay in the pieces [5].

Analysis and discussion

To study the possibilities of using waste glass as an aggregate for the production of the first concrete samples, gravel with a fraction of 5-10 mm, natural sand and waste glass with a dispersion of 0-10 mm were used as a fine aggregate. Plastic concrete mixture was included by replacing sand with glass in amounts of 0, 30, 50, 70 and 100% of the mass of fine aggregate. The composition of the concrete mixture is presented in table 4.

Table 4

The composition of the concrete mixture

The content of the glass fraction in the mass of fine aggregate, %	0	30	50	70	100
Unit	kq/m ³				
Cement	716	716	700	698	696
Natural sand	967	676	477	284	0
Waste glass	0	292	476	666	944
Gravel 5 - 10 mm	267	265	263	261	261
Water	333	333	322	324	321
Water cement ratio	0,46	0,46	0,46	0,46	0,46
Average density, kq/m ³	2273	2273	2246	2236	2216

Concrete samples of 40 x 40 x 160 mm size made from concrete mixture with different composition were kept for 7 and 28 days under normal hardening conditions. The compressive strength of concrete samples is

given in terms of the tensile strength of standard samples.

The results of the study are given in figure 1:

Fig. 1 Dependence of concrete strength on the amount of waste glass

Table 5

Indicators of the compressive strength limit of the samples according to the percentage of the filler glass mass (Mpa)

Storage time of samples	Amount of bottle as filler				
	0%	30%	50%	70%	100%
7 days	3.22	2.75	3.04	2.96	2.87
28 days	4.64	4.22	4.23	4.33	4.31

Studies have shown that when 30% of pomegranate sand is replaced by glass, the strength of concrete decreases by about 9% in a 28-day sample, and a slight increase in concrete strength is observed with further increase in the proportion of glass in pomegranate aggregate. When 70% of fine sand is replaced with glass, the strength of 28-day concrete decreases by 7%. It can be said that when glass is added to the aggregates, the pomegranate decreases the strength of the concrete, the glass grains have a smooth surface, and they do not adhere well to the cement stone.

Crushed granite was used as aggregate for other samples to increase the strength of the concrete samples. Samples were prepared using crushed sand and gravel fractions with a particle size of 0-10 mm and fractions of 5-10 mm, as a fine aggregate - granite. Glass was added to the plastic concrete mixture in the following amounts of fine aggregate mass, and the corresponding amount of sand was replaced with glass. Normally hardening dolomite cement was used as a binder. The mobility of this concrete mix was assumed as developed above. The composition of the concrete mixture is presented in Table 6.

Table 6

The composition of the concrete mixture.

Number of samples	1	2	3	4	5	6
The content of glass from the aggregate mass of pomegranate, %	0	15	30	50	70	100
Unit	kg/m ³					
Cement	586	582	587	586	581	576
Sand	837	705	588	417	248	0
Glass	0	126	253	419	578	825
Granite gravel, 5 - 10 mm	626	624	632	626	621	619
Water	294	290	296	294	291	288
Water cement ratio	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Average density, kg/m ³	2338	2326	2356	2343	2323	2306

Fig. 2 Views of the samples before and after experimental testing

Table 7

Results of strength tests of concrete

Sample number	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Fractional size of waste glass, mm	5-10	2.5-5	1.25-2.5	0,65-1.25	0,315-0.65	0,16-0.315	< 0,16
Unit	kg/m ³						
Cement	587	584	577	573	575	572	617
Sand	418	417	412	410	411	409	365
Broken glass	420	419	414	410	411	409	365
Granite gravel 5-10 mm	627	629	618	617	616	613	544
Water	294	293	289	285	288	287	307
Water cement ratio	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Average density, kg/m ³	2347	2338	2312	2290	2297	2288	2196

According to the test results, the durability of concrete samples made from crushed granite sand is higher than that of natural ordinary sand.

An increase in the glass content of 15% gravel sand in crushed granite sand leads to a decrease in the strength of smooth concrete. It reduces the strength of concrete by about 11.2% compared to the complete replacement of crushed sand with granite sand.

A third batch of concrete samples was prepared to study the effect of glass of different sizes on the properties of concrete. In this batch of concrete samples,

granite gravel with a fraction of 5-10 mm was used as filler, sand and glass fractions made of granite as fine filler: <0.16; 0.16-0.315; 0.315-0.63; 0.63-1.25; 1.25-2.5; 2.5-5; 5-10 mm. It is made by replacing the mass of fine aggregate, 50% of gravel sand with the same amount of glass in the plastic concrete mix. The composition of the concrete mixture is presented in table 7.

When glass shards with particle sizes in the range of 0.16-0.315 mm were used, the concrete mixture became hard, which is explained by the increase in the specific surface of the pomegranate particles.

Fig. 3. Bending strength limit after drying for 7 days

When glass shards with a particle size of less than 0.16 mm are used as a filler, it is observed that the mixture is too hard and not workable. To improve the workability, water and cement were added to the concrete mixture in the amount of 20% of the mass.

Fig. 4. Compressive strength limit after drying for 7 days

Dolomite cement was used for the preparation of concrete samples. The strength of the prepared concrete samples was tested after 7 and 28 days of storage

RESULTS

1. An increase in water resistance of concrete obtained on the basis of cement, waste glass and granite powder was determined.

2. Depending on the amount of waste taken, the flexural strength value of the concrete samples was between 2.22 Mpa and 6.04 Mpa, while the 0% waste concrete sample taken for comparison was 5.5 Mpa. The compressive strength limit was between 5.5 Mpa and 10.55 Mpa has been between

3. The optimal content of zeolite-containing rock additives in dolomite cement is 5%, which leads to an increase in the density and softening coefficient of concrete based on dolomite cement up to 0.73, as well as a decrease in total porosity.

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